

Securing the Digital Frontier: A Vision for Responsible Digital Citizenship

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Abstract

This paper proposes the introduction of idea to a government-issued email ID linked to digital identification (like Aadhaar) issued by Government as a solution to mitigate the negative effects of anonymity on the internet. By integrating such a system into existing internet platforms, this initiative aims to enhance accountability, curb cybercrime, and ensure secure digital spaces. With blockchain and API-based data-sharing mechanisms, the system emphasizes user privacy while fostering trust and authenticity in online interactions. The paper discusses implementation, benefits, challenges, and feasibility, while citing relevant data and past events to highlight the pressing need for such a system. This initiative not only addresses challenges of cybercrime and misinformation but also establishes a scalable model for responsible digital citizenship globally.

1. Introduction

The internet has revolutionized communication, commerce, and access to information. The widespread use of internet makes it very useful as well as very harmful for people. The anonymity it provides has facilitated cybercrimes at a very large scale, misinformation and rumours to spread like wildfire, and online abuse with adults as well as minors.

A study by PRAHAR revealed that cyberattacks on India alone reached 79 million in 2023 and in Q1 of 2024 there are already 500 million incidents blocked. In the first four months of 2024, Indians lost more than ₹1,750 crore to cyber criminals. These numbers are expected to cross 17 trillion by 2047. Cybercrime is predicted to cost the world \$8 trillion USD in 2023, according to Cybersecurity Ventures.

In 2022 alone, India witnessed over **13.91 lakh cyber incidents**, according to the Indian Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT-In). Fake news has repeatedly led to violent incidents; for example, **25 lynching cases in 2018** were reportedly triggered by rumours spread through social media platforms like WhatsApp. Such incidents highlight the urgent need for mechanisms that ensure accountability while safeguarding user privacy.

This paper proposes a government-issued email ID system linked to Aadhaar-like identification to address these challenges.

2. The Proposed System

2.1 Overview

Each citizen has a digital identification these days and this ID can be linked to an e-mail ID which will be issued by the government. Each citizen receives a government-issued e-mail ID linked to their digital identification (e.g., Aadhaar). This e-mail ID will be used by the citizens and users around the internet to create profiles on different platforms. This ID is used solely for account creation on online platforms, ensuring accountability without compromising privacy.

2.2 Key Features

- **Integration:**
 - Different platforms adopt "Sign in with Government ID," allowing users to sign in with the e-mail ID they received by the government.
 - During the time of sign in user will be notified what data is being shared with the platform and users control what data is shared.
 - In the future if user wants to remove access to the data on the platform, they can remove it.
- **Privacy:**
 - The system will be backed by Blockchain or API-based systems to prevent unauthorized access to user data.
- **Authentication:**
 - Multi-level authentication will be embedded into the system so that user needs to enter an extra OTP or click the prompt on their primary mobiles to permit the sign in.
 - This will ensure the user authenticity.
- **Platform Compliance:**
 - Platforms and Companies seeking to use this feature must justify data usage and adhere to government regulations.

- Each platform needs to sign up for this system with the government to ensure platform's authenticity.
- Every platform will be given a badge to put on their website.

3. Benefits

3.1 Enhanced Accountability and Trust

- Because of this system now real identities are linked to online accounts, which makes tracing cybercrimes and identifying perpetrators straightforward, convenient and easy.
- Online interactions and transactions will become more trustworthy, as now the person knows that the other person behind the screen is a real and authentic person, encouraging digital commerce and collaboration.
- Businesses benefit from reduced risks of fraud and fake profiles, simplifying operations like customer verification and KYC.

3.2 Improved Cybersecurity

- This system supports multi-level authentication which reduces the risk of account takeovers.
- Only limited data from users' digital identity will be shared with the platform. Thus, in case of data breach only minimum data will be compromised.

3.3 Reduction in Misinformation

- The system will allow each account to be automatically verified, which will end the fake profiles, which are major source of misinformation.
- It will enhance the traceability of person who spreads the misinformation helping in curbing the spread of fake news.

3.4 Digital Citizenship

- The system will start a new chapter in Digital Citizenships, empowering citizens in the only spaces.
- It aligns with various digitalization programs (Digital India etc.) around the globe making digital literacy more convenient.

3.5 Age Restrictions and Parental Controls

- The system will have real and certified data of each person thus it will make it easy to restrict content based on age and other parameters.
 - Such as ban on social media by Australia.
- Enforces age-appropriate platform usage, addressing global concerns about children's safety on social media.
- The email of minors can be linked with the email of their guardian, which will give a better parental control.
 - This will automatically unlink after legal age of the respective country.

3.6 Economic Benefits

- It will encourage foreign and domestic businesses to engage in country's digital economy by ensuring verified, trustworthy user bases.
- This will allow MNCs to localize the data of a particular country.
 - Which will reduce data centralization, reducing the risk of data breach future.
 - It will also create jobs for the local people and help in infrastructure development in the country.

4. Supporting Evidence

4.1 Misinformation and Fake News

World faced a significant rise in misinformation and fake news. The misinformation is usually increased and used at the time of elections around the world to manipulate the decisions of the citizens. Some major incidents are:

- **2016 U.S. Presidential Election (Russian Disinformation Campaign)**
 - **Incident:** During the 2016 U.S. presidential election, Russian operatives used social media to spread misinformation and disinformation to sow division among Americans. This included fake news stories, conspiracy theories, and inflammatory content aimed at influencing voter behaviour.

- **Impact:** The spread of fake news contributed to political polarization, distrust in institutions, and even violence. The event raised concerns about the vulnerability of democratic processes to external manipulation.
- **Source:** Investigations led by U.S. intelligence agencies and subsequent Senate hearings confirmed the widespread nature of this disinformation campaign.

There are other incidents those were caused by the fake news:

- **COVID-19 Misinformation (Global)**

- **Incident:** Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, fake news and conspiracy theories proliferated, claiming that the virus was a hoax, that 5G technology caused the virus, or that certain cures (like bleach or hydroxychloroquine) were effective.
- **Impact:** Misinformation led to public health risks, delays in vaccination uptake, and harm from unproven treatments. Governments and health organizations around the world had to combat both the virus and the wave of misinformation.
- **Source:** World Health Organization (WHO) and various governments have documented the spread of fake health information during the pandemic.

- **Myanmar Rohingya Genocide (2017)**

- **Incident:** In Myanmar, false reports and inflammatory social media posts fuelled hatred and violence against the Rohingya Muslim minority, leading to a brutal military crackdown. Rumours and false stories about the Rohingya committing violence were spread, exacerbating ethnic tensions.
- **Impact:** The misinformation contributed to widespread violence, with thousands of deaths and hundreds of thousands of Rohingya people displaced. The UN and human rights groups later identified this as a genocide.
- **Source:** Reports by the United Nations and international human rights organizations highlighted the role of social media in spreading hate speech.

- **Pizzagate (2016, United States)**

- **Incident:** A conspiracy theory emerged claiming that a Washington, D.C., pizzeria (Comet Ping Pong) was a front for a child sex trafficking ring involving high-profile political figures

like Hillary Clinton and her associates. The theory was spread through social media platforms like Reddit and Twitter.

- **Impact:** The conspiracy theory led to a man armed with a rifle entering the pizzeria, firing shots, and demanding answers. No one was harmed, but the event raised concerns about the real-world consequences of online conspiracy theories.
- **Source:** Investigations later showed that "Pizzagate" was entirely false, yet the viral spread of the theory had led to physical harm and fear.
- **Indian Anti-Vaccine Movement (2018-2020)**
 - **Incident:** A series of viral social media posts and WhatsApp messages spread misinformation about the safety and efficacy of vaccines, particularly the polio vaccine in India. This misinformation included false claims that vaccines were harmful and caused diseases.
 - **Impact:** Vaccine hesitancy led to outbreaks of preventable diseases such as polio and measles in certain regions of India. Efforts by the Indian government and global health organizations to combat misinformation helped reduce the impact.
 - **Source:** WHO and the Indian government worked on debunking false vaccine claims, but misinformation spread by WhatsApp remained a major challenge.

These all are results of a misinformation or fake news spread by some anonymous users on the internet. The anonymity of internet, which once was a blessing has now become a curse for the larger cause.

5. Implementation

5.1 Mobile-Based Registration

An e-mail ID along with the government ID (like Aadhaar) will be issued to citizens. Those who have already issued IDs can get their new government e-mail ID from an online portal by applying. Support will be provided through government offices, kiosks, or any other partner organizations such as NGOs for those needing assistance.

5.2 Integration with Platforms

- Platforms, such as Facebook and Instagram, implement the system through APIs. Users will control what data to share with the platform during account creation and can revoke permission anytime in the future.
- The users who already have an account on platform can also link their account to their new government e-mail ID.

5.3 Data Localization and Security

- Platforms and companies will be required to store data within the country.
- Blockchain and other latest & advance technologies will ensure secure, tamper-proof data handling.

5.4 Multi-Level Authentication

- OTPs verification will be required for login.
- Notification will be sent to user for every login, and if user found it suspicious, they can instantly lock their profile and report it to authorities.
 - This will prevent unlawful usage of someone's account by the hackers or any other user.

6. Addressing Concerns

6.1 Privacy Scepticism

- Government will only work as an authentication provider during account creation. After it all the data of the users will be handled by the platforms.
 - The data can be requested in case of mishappening.
- Transparent audits will be conducted to ensure that the government do not have access to data of a platform.
 - Regular third-party audits will ensure compliance, with public reports to maintain transparency and build public trust.
- Companies and platforms will have to sign up with government before they could use this authentication system.
 - During this they must justify what data they need and why?

- Only data which has allowed to platform during sign up with government will be allowed to access by the platform.
- Every data which is shared to the platform will be notified and approved by the user and they can revoke the permission at any time.

6.2 Compliance by Platforms

- Non-compliant platforms risk losing access to the local market, a key revenue source for global companies.

6.3 Inclusivity

- Public private partnership will be made to cover more population in this system. NGOs and local authorities assist less tech-savvy populations in adopting the system.
- Alternatives like manual identity verification are available for citizens without Aadhaar or digital IDs.

7. Feasibility and Cost Analysis

- The system will be majority automatic, but for backup there will be a team at the background to solve queries and complaints.
- Initial investment for infrastructure and personnel will be required.
- Public-private partnership and investment by the giants like Meta and Google in local development can offset initial costs.

8. Future Applications

- The e-mail can be used to access public services and schemes, streamlining the process and making government operations more transparent.

9. Conclusion

The proposed government-issued e-mail ID authentication system offers a balanced approach. It guarantees users the privacy while ensuring them about the authenticity of the person on the other side of the screen. It allows government and authorities to trace misinformation and fake news. By

addressing challenges and leveraging advanced technologies, this initiative can transform world's digital landscape and serve as a global benchmark for cybersecurity and governance.

10. References

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